

Derivation of the Lorentz Transformation from Two Way Light Speed and Velocity Reciprocity

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Abstract: We demonstrate that the Lorentz transformation can be derived from two operationally definable and empirically grounded postulates: (i) the isotropy of the two-way speed of light, and (ii) the reciprocity of radar-measured velocities between inertial frames. Introducing an "Einstein gauge" decouples synchronization conventions from kinematics, allowing the transformation to be obtained without the *a priori* assumption of one-way light speed constancy. This framework shows that the synchronization anisotropy parameter κ —traditionally viewed as a conventional degree of freedom—must vanish if velocity reciprocity holds. The one-way speed emerges as a consequence of these minimal axioms. The result provides a minimal axiomatic basis for special relativity and identifies velocity reciprocity as a testable condition accessible to current GNSS and radar technologies.

1. Introduction

Einstein's two postulates—the principle of relativity and the constancy of the speed of light—form the standard axiomatic basis of special relativity [1]. While strongly supported by experiment, these postulates are not directly verifiable in isolation. The principle of relativity is a broad statement about the equivalence of inertial frames, and the constancy of the one-way speed of light depends on a choice of clock synchronization convention [2]. In practice, only the *round-trip* (two-way) speed of light is directly measurable, and it has been experimentally shown to be isotropic and frame-independent to high precision [3–5].

In this work, we show that the Lorentz transformation can be recovered from a more minimal and operationally grounded set of postulates: (i) the isotropy of the two-way speed of light, which is already well verified, and (ii) the reciprocity of radar-measured velocities between inertial frames $w = -v$, which is testable but not yet directly confirmed as a foundational symmetry. In this framework, the constancy of the one-way speed of light emerges as a consequence, rather than being postulated, and any physical synchronization anisotropy κ [6] must vanish if reciprocity holds. Thus, confirming velocity reciprocity would empirically establish the one-way isotropy of light as a mathematical necessity within the theory.

The idea of deriving the Lorentz transformation from postulates weaker than Einstein's has a long history. Ignatowski [7] and later authors [8–10] showed that the relativity principle alone, together with homogeneity and isotropy, leads to a transformation with an invariant speed, which may later be identified with c . These derivations treat the invariant speed as a free parameter and do not explicitly address the role of synchronization in connecting it to light. Meanwhile, the conventionality of simultaneity—articulated by Reichenbach [11] and formalized by Winnie [12,13]—highlights the freedom in synchronizing distant clocks, often parameterized by κ . This freedom leaves the one-way speed of light conventionally chosen rather than empirically fixed, a point further developed in test theories such as those of Mansouri–Sexl [14] and Robertson [15].

Our approach bridges these two lines of inquiry. Starting only from two-way light speed isotropy, we introduce an *Einstein gauge* to handle synchronization choices explicitly. Imposing kinematic reciprocity then uniquely selects the Lorentz transformation and

forces κ to vanish. The derivation does not assume the one-way constancy of light, which instead emerges as a consequence of velocity reciprocity¹.

The result is a minimal axiomatic basis for special relativity that is both empirically grounded and open to direct experimental test via radar or satellite-based measurements of velocity reciprocity [16,17].

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 defines physical and Einstein-gauge coordinates and introduces the synchronization parameter κ . Section 3 presents the step-by-step derivation of the transformation. Section 4 examines the physical implications for κ and synchronization conventions. Section 5 summarizes the results and suggests directions for experimental verification.

2.1 Clock Synchronization and the Anisotropy Parameter

Let S be an inertial frame. We wish to assign time and space coordinates (t,x,y,z) to events. The assignment of space coordinates is straightforward using a rigid ruler at rest in S . The assignment of a time coordinate t to distant events requires a synchronization convention for clocks at different spatial locations.

A common empirical procedure to synchronize two clocks is to use light signals. Consider a light signal emitted from the origin at $t=0$, reflected at a distant point with position vector \mathbf{r} , and received back at the origin. Let τ_{emit} and τ_{rec} be the emission and reception times recorded by a clock at the origin. The two-way (round-trip) speed of light c is defined operationally as

¹ Conversely, if one postulates the universal and isotropic one-way speed of light, the measured velocities between frames become reciprocal, which in turn implies the mathematical form of the relativity principle. Thus, either reciprocity or one-way light isotropy can be taken as the starting postulate; the other follows as a consequence.

$$c = \frac{2 |\mathbf{r}|}{\tau_{rec} - \tau_{emit}} \quad (2.1)$$

Experiment confirms that this quantity is independent of the direction of \mathbf{r} and of the location of the experiment [3,4], with modern precision tests further constraining any anisotropy [5,18,19].

To assign a time coordinate t to the reflection event, we must decide how to split the total travel time ($\tau_{rec} - \tau_{emit}$) into an outward and a return leg. Let t_{out} be the coordinate time for the light to travel from the origin to \mathbf{r} , and t_{back} the time for the return trip. We have

$$t_{out} + t_{back} = \tau_{rec} - \tau_{emit} = \frac{2 |\mathbf{r}|}{c} \quad (2.2)$$

The most general linear rule for assigning t_{out} and t_{back} consistent with (2.2) is

$$t_{out} = \frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{c} (1 - \boldsymbol{\kappa}' \hat{\mathbf{r}}), \quad t_{back} = \frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{c} (1 + \boldsymbol{\kappa}' \hat{\mathbf{r}}) \quad (2.3)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{r}/|\mathbf{r}|$ and $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ is a dimensionless vector constant characteristic of the synchronization convention chosen in frame S.

The corresponding one-way coordinate speeds of light in the direction $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ are then

$$c_{out}(\hat{\mathbf{r}}) = \frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{t_{out}} = \frac{c}{(1 - \boldsymbol{\kappa}' \hat{\mathbf{r}})} \quad \text{and} \quad c_{back}(\hat{\mathbf{r}}) = \frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{t_{back}} = \frac{c}{(1 + \boldsymbol{\kappa}' \hat{\mathbf{r}})} \quad (2.4)$$

Thus, the choice of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ determines the anisotropy pattern of the coordinate one-way light speed. The value $\boldsymbol{\kappa}=\mathbf{0}$ yields isotropic one-way speeds $c_{out}=c_{back}=c$ and it is Einstein synchronization. A non-zero $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ represents anisotropic propagation of light as described in that frame's coordinates.

Within the conventionality literature, $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ is typically treated as a convention—a free parameter in our description of physics [2,6]. However, an equally consistent interpretation is that $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ could represent a physical property of spacetime [6, 14,15]. Our current experimental capabilities, which rely on closed light paths, cannot distinguish a universe with $\boldsymbol{\kappa}=\mathbf{0}$ from one with any other fixed $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ [6,16,17]. We therefore begin our analysis from the most general by assuming that each inertial frame may possess a fixed, intrinsic (though unknown) anisotropy vector $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$. The coordinates reflecting this true anisotropy are termed the *physical coordinates* of the frame, denoted by $(\bar{t}, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$.

2.2 The Einstein Gauge as a Mathematical Tool

It is mathematically convenient to transform physical coordinates to a system where the one-way light speed is isotropic by *definition*. We define the *Einstein-gauge coordinates* (t, x, y, z) for a frame via the linear transformation

$$\begin{pmatrix} t \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = U(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) \begin{pmatrix} \bar{t} \\ \bar{x} \\ \bar{y} \\ \bar{z} \end{pmatrix}, \quad U(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \kappa_x/c & \kappa_y/c & \kappa_z/c \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

The spatial coordinates are unchanged, as they are tied to a material ruler at rest. The time coordinate is rescaled and shifted to absorb the anisotropy. By construction, in the Einstein gauge the one-way speed of light is isotropic and equal to a constant, which we denote by c for the frame S . Crucially, this c is the same two-way constant appearing in (2.1); the transformation (2.5) merely redistributes the time coordinate along different paths to achieve formal isotropy.

If the physical universe has $\boldsymbol{\kappa} \neq \mathbf{0}$, then the Einstein gauge is a useful computational fiction—a *mathematical tool* rather than a description of reality [10,18,19]. Different inertial frames, with different physical $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$, will have different Einstein-gauge transformations. Consequently, the constants representing the isotropic one-way light

speed in different inertial frames are *a priori* independent parameters. They are related to the (unknown) physical anisotropies and the universal two-way speed. This perspective explicitly retains the possibility that the "constant speed of light" may differ between frames.

2.3 General Transformation Between Frames

Let S and S_v be two inertial frames in standard configuration, with S_v moving along the common x -axis relative to S . Let their physical coordinates be $(\bar{t}, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$ and $(\bar{t}_v, \bar{x}_v, \bar{y}_v, \bar{z}_v)$, characterized by intrinsic anisotropy vectors $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ and $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_v$, respectively. Homogeneity and isotropy of space (in the sense of no preferred *location* or transverse *direction*) imply that the transformation between these physical coordinates is linear. We denote this physical transformation matrix by $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \bar{t}_v \\ \bar{x}_v \\ \bar{y}_v \\ \bar{z}_v \end{pmatrix} = \bar{\mathbf{M}} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{t} \\ \bar{x} \\ \bar{y} \\ \bar{z} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

The explicit form of $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$ will involve parameters describing the relative motion and the anisotropies.

Applying the gauge transformations (2.5) to both sides of (2.6) allows us to express the relationship in the computationally convenient Einstein gauges.

$$\mathbf{U}_v(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) \begin{pmatrix} t_v \\ x_v \\ y_v \\ z_v \end{pmatrix} = \bar{\mathbf{M}} \mathbf{U}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) \begin{pmatrix} t \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.7)$$

We define the *Einstein-gauge transformation matrix* \mathbf{M} as the linear map between the Einstein-gauge coordinates of the two frames:

$$\begin{pmatrix} t_v \\ x_v \\ y_v \\ z_v \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{M} \begin{pmatrix} t \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.8)$$

Comparing the two expressions, we obtain the central relation that separates the (possibly physical) synchronization anisotropies from the core kinematic transformation:

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{U}^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}_v) \bar{\mathbf{M}} \mathbf{U}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) \quad (2.9)$$

The matrix \mathbf{M} contains the essential kinematics as viewed through the lens of isotropic gauges. All dependence on the unknown physical anisotropies $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ and $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_v$ is confined to the outer \mathbf{U} -matrices. In the following section, we determine the most general form of \mathbf{M} using only operational definitions and the empirically secure postulate of two-way light speed invariance, treating c and c_v as independent parameters until further constraints are imposed.

This framework allows us to cleanly analyze the transformation structure without presupposing the universality of the one-way light speed or the principle of relativity. The Lorentz transformation, along with the universality of the constant c , will emerge within this Einstein-gauge formalism as a special case corresponding to specific additional kinematic conventions applied to \mathbf{M} .

3. Solving the Einstein-Gauge Transformation

The following subsections progressively determine the general form of the Einstein-gauge transformation matrix \mathbf{M} by applying a series of definitions, requirements, conditions, and physical postulates. Each one is stated at the beginning of a subsection and leads to a specific constraint(s) on the matrix elements, ultimately reducing the number of free parameters.

3.1 Alignment of the Line of Relative Motion

Definition: *The frames S and S_v are in standard configuration. Their relative motion is along the common x -axis, and their spatial origins coincide at the event chosen as the coordinate origin.*

This operational definition has direct mathematical consequences. The Einstein-gauge coordinates (t, x, y, z) and (t_v, x_v, y_v, z_v) , are defined by the condition that synchronization is performed using isotropic one-way light speed. Crucially, in these coordinates, for all coordinate times t in S , the set of points with $y=z=0$ (the x -axis) must map to the set of points in S_v with $y_v=z_v=0$ (the x_v -axis). This is not merely a condition on spatial locations, but on entire worldlines.

The worldline of a point on the x -axis in S is $(t, x, 0, 0)$ for all t and x . Its image in S_v must satisfy $y_v=z_v=0$ for all t and x . Applying the Einstein-gauge transformation \mathbf{M} from Eq. (2.8):

$$y_v = M_{yt} t + M_{yx} x = 0, \quad z_v = M_{zt} t + M_{zx} x = 0$$

must hold for all t and x . This global vanishing is possible only if the coefficients of both t and x are independently zero. Therefore,

$$M_{yx} = M_{zx} = M_{yt} = M_{zt} = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

Applying the identical reasoning in the inverse direction (the worldline of the x_v -axis in S_v must map to the x -axis in S) yields the symmetric conditions:

$$M_{xy} = M_{xz} = M_{ty} = M_{tz} = 0 \quad (3.2)$$

Therefore, in the Einstein gauge, the alignment condition forces the transformation matrix \mathbf{M} to be block-diagonal:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{tt} & M_{tx} & 0 & 0 \\ M_{xt} & M_{xx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & M_{yy} & M_{yz} \\ 0 & 0 & M_{zy} & M_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.3)$$

This is a significant simplification. The synchronization convention of the Einstein gauge eliminates the possibility of a transformation that "tilts" the time coordinate relative to transverse spatial axes, which is permitted in the more general physical coordinates [6,14,20].

3.2 Isotropy of the Transverse Plane

Requirement: *Space is isotropic in all planes perpendicular to the line of relative motion. No unique direction within the transverse y-z plane is physically distinguished.*

This is a postulate about physical space, and therefore it must be reflected in the transformation between the physical coordinates of any two frames. Consequently, the Einstein-gauge transformation \mathbf{M} , derived from the physical transformation via Eq. (2.9), must also respect this symmetry. This spatial symmetry implies that the transformation between frames must be invariant under arbitrary rotations of the coordinate system around the common x-axis. Let $\mathbf{R}(\phi)$ be the matrix representing a rotation by an angle ϕ in the y-z plane:

$$\mathbf{R}(\phi) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cos \phi & -\sin \phi \\ 0 & 0 & \sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.4)$$

The requirement of transverse isotropy is enforced by demanding that the transformation matrix \mathbf{M} commutes with this rotation [20]:

$$\mathbf{M} \mathbf{R}(\phi) = \mathbf{R}(\phi) \mathbf{M} \quad \text{for all } \phi \quad (3.5)$$

Substituting the block-diagonal form of \mathbf{M} from Eq. (3.3) into condition (3.4) isolates the constraint on the 2x2 transverse block. Let

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{yy} & M_{yz} \\ M_{zy} & M_{zz} \end{bmatrix}$$

Equation (3.5) for the transverse sector reduces to:

$$\mathbf{T} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi & -\sin \phi \\ \sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi & -\sin \phi \\ \sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.6)$$

A 2x2 matrix \mathbf{T} satisfies (3.6) if and only if it is a scalar multiple of the identity matrix. Applying (3.6) for specific angles (e.g., $\phi=\pi/2$) or analyzing the infinitesimal generator of rotations forces the conditions $M_{yz}=-M_{zy}$ and $M_{yy}=M_{zz}$, while the full continuous symmetry demands the off-diagonal elements vanish and the diagonal elements be equal. The unique solution is:

$$M_{yz}=M_{zy}=0, \quad M_{yy}=M_{zz}=f \quad (3.7)$$

where f is a scalar function of the relative motion and the gauge light speeds.

Substituting this result into Eq. (3.3) yields the refined form of the Einstein-gauge transformation:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & 0 & 0 \\ d & e & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & f & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & f \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.8)$$

The parameters a, b, d, e govern the transformation in the time-longitudinal sector, while f is the transverse scale factor. All are functions to be determined by subsequent postulates.

3.3 Definition of Relative Velocity and its Einstein-Gauge Expression

Definition: *The relative motion between frames is characterized by a constant physical velocity \bar{v} . The Einstein-gauge coordinate velocity v of S_v in S is defined as the derivative of its spatial coordinate with respect to its time coordinate, both expressed in the Einstein gauge of S .*

We must carefully distinguish:

- \bar{v} : The physical speed, measured using clocks and rulers synchronized according to the (possibly anisotropic) physical synchronization of frame S .
- v : The speed assigned within the Einstein-gauge coordinates of S , where synchronization is defined to be isotropic.

The physical velocity \bar{v} of the origin of S_v is defined in physical coordinates (\bar{t}, \bar{x}) of S .

For an event on its worldline, $\bar{x} = \bar{v} \bar{t}$.

We relate this to the Einstein-gauge coordinates (t, x) via the anisotropy transformation

(2.5): $t = \bar{t} + \frac{\kappa_x}{c} \bar{x}$ and $x = \bar{x}$. Substituting the worldline condition gives:

$$x = \bar{v} \left(t - \frac{\kappa_x}{c} x \right)$$

Solving for x as a function of t yields:

$$x(t) = \frac{\bar{v}}{1 - \frac{\bar{v} \kappa_x}{c}} t$$

Thus, velocity in Einstein-gauge analysis, v , is related to the physical speed, \bar{v} , and the synchronization anisotropy, κ_x , of frame S :

$$v = \frac{\bar{v}}{1 - \frac{\bar{v} \kappa_x}{c}} \quad (3.9)$$

The worldline of the origin of S_v is $(t_v, 0, 0, 0)$ in its own Einstein-gauge coordinates. Applying the transformation matrix \mathbf{M} from (3.8) to its expression in S , $(t, x, 0, 0)$, where $x = v t$, gives:

$$\begin{pmatrix} t_v \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & 0 & 0 \\ d & e & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & f & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & f \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} t \\ v t \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (a + b v) t \\ (d + e v) t \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

From the second row, we obtain new restriction on \mathbf{M} :

$$d = -e v \quad (3.10)$$

This restriction is a direct consequence of defining the relative speed v within the Einstein-gauge coordinate system. Substituting (3.10) into (3.8) gives the constrained form of the transformation:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & 0 & 0 \\ -e v & e & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & f & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & f \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.11)$$

The remaining parameters will be determined by postulates concerning light propagation and the consistency of the transformation law.

3.4 Isotropy of the Round-Trip Speed of Light

Postulate: *The round-trip (two-way) speed of light is isotropic in every inertial frame [3,418,19].*

We apply this empirically based postulate using a thought experiment in frame S_v . A light signal is emitted from the origin of S_v at $t_v=0$, propagates a proper distance R_v at an angle θ in the $x_v y_v$ -plane, reflects off a mirror, and returns to the origin. In S_v , the physical round-trip light travel time over a fixed proper distance R_v is isotropic and equal to $2 R_v/c_v$ due to the empirical postulate. This physical time is unchanged by the

transformation to Einstein-gauge coordinates. Therefore, in the Einstein gauge of S_v , the total coordinate time is also isotropic (independent of θ) and given by $T_v^R = 2R_v/c_v$, where c_v is the isotropic one-way light speed defined in that gauge.

We describe this same physical process in the Einstein-gauge coordinates of S . Let the reflection event have coordinates $(T1, X, Y, 0)$ in S . Let the return event, where light arrives back at the moving origin of S_v , have coordinates $(T2, v T2, 0, 0)$ in S .

The transformation \mathbf{M} from (3.11) and the fact that the mirror is at rest in S_v give the relations for the reflection event:

$$R_v \cos \theta = -v e T1 + e X, \quad R_v \sin \theta = f Y \quad (3.12)$$

From the second equation, $Y = \frac{R_v}{f} \sin \theta$. From the first, $X = v T1 + \frac{R_v}{f} \cos \theta$.

In the Einstein gauge of S , light propagates isotropically with speed c . For the outgoing leg:

$$X^2 + Y^2 = c^2 T1^2 \quad (3.13)$$

Substituting the expressions for X and Y gives an equation for $T1$:

$$\left(v T1 + \frac{R_v}{f} \cos \theta \right)^2 + \left(\frac{R_v}{f} \sin \theta \right)^2 = c^2 T1^2 \quad (3.14)$$

For the return leg, light travels from $(T1, X, Y, 0)$ to $(T2, v T2, 0, 0)$. The light speed condition gives:

$$(X - v T2)^2 + Y^2 = c^2 (T2 - T1)^2 \quad (3.15)$$

Solving the system of equations (3.14) and (3.15) yields $T2$ and $T1$ as a function of θ :

$$T1^2 = \frac{1}{c^2} \left[\frac{1}{f^2} R_v^2 \sin^2 \theta + \frac{1}{e^2} (R_v \cos \theta + e v T1)^2 \right] \quad (3.16)$$

$$T2 = 2 T1 - \frac{2 v R_v \cos \theta}{e (c^2 - v^2)} \quad (3.17)$$

The empirical postulate requires that the total time T_2 is independent of the orientation θ . Therefore, we impose:

$$\frac{dT_2}{d\theta} = 0 \quad \text{for all } \theta \quad (3.18)$$

Carrying out this differentiation using (3.16) and (3.17) and setting the result to zero yields, after simplification, the condition:

$$c^2(e^2 - f^2) - v^2 e^2 = 0 \quad (3.19)$$

Solving for the transverse scale factor f gives the constraint imposed by two-way light speed isotropy:

$$f = e \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \quad (3.20)$$

Substituting this result into (3.11) gives the transformation matrix constrained by both the definition of relative speed and the two-way light postulate:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & 0 & 0 \\ -e v & e & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & e \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.21)$$

The parameters a , b , and e remain free.

3.5 Internal Consistency of the Transformation Law

Condition: The law transforming coordinates from S to S_v must be internally consistent. Specifically, performing the identical operational procedure (the two-way light speed experiment) with the roles of the frames reversed must yield a transformation that is the mathematical inverse of the original.

This postulate enforces that the transformation structure is not arbitrary but must respect the symmetry of the physical setup [15, 17, 19]. We consider the inverse experiment: frame S is now the "moving" emitter, and frame S_v is the "laboratory" frame. Repeating the analysis of Sections 3.3 and 3.4 from this perspective yields an Einstein-gauge transformation matrix \mathbf{M}_v for the coordinates of S in terms of those of S_v . Its form, by the identical derivation, must be:

$$\mathbf{M}_v = \begin{bmatrix} a_v & b_v & 0 & 0 \\ -e_v w & e_v & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e_v \sqrt{1 - \frac{w^2}{c_v^2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & e_v \sqrt{1 - \frac{w^2}{c_v^2}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.22)$$

where w is the Einstein-gauge speed of S as measured in S_v , c_v is the isotropic light speed in the S_v gauge, and a_v, b_v, e_v are the analogous parameters.

The consistency condition requires that the transformation from S_v to S is the inverse of the transformation from S to S_v . Therefore,

$$\mathbf{M}_v = \mathbf{M}^{-1} \quad (3.23)$$

We compute \mathbf{M}^{-1} from the general form (3.21). Equating \mathbf{M}_v to \mathbf{M}^{-1} element-by-element yields a set of equations. The most illuminating relation comes from comparing the (2,1) elements:

$$-w e_v = \frac{v e}{a e + v b e} \quad (3.24)$$

and the (2,2) elements:

$$e_v = \frac{a}{a + v b} \quad (3.25)$$

Dividing equation (3.24) by equation (3.25) cancels the common factor involving the denominator, yielding a simple relation between the leading parameters of the two transformations:

$$a = -e \frac{v}{w} \quad (3.26)$$

Furthermore based on the equality of the transverse elements (3,3) of \mathbf{M}_v and \mathbf{M}^{-1} we obtain:

$$e e_v = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{w^2}{c_v^2}} \quad (3.27)$$

Equations (3.26) and (3.27) are a direct consequence of the internal consistency requirement \mathbf{M}_v to \mathbf{M}^{-1} . (3.26) links the time-scaling parameter a in one direction to the velocity ratio v/w and the longitudinal scale e , which is in turn restricted by (3.27).

3.6 Invariance of the Light-like Interval

Postulate: Events connected by a light signal in one Einstein-gauge coordinate system are also connected by a light signal in the other. Formally, a worldline satisfying $dx/dt = \pm c$ in frame S must transform to a worldline satisfying $dx_v/dt_v = \pm c_v$ frame S_v , where the sign corresponds to the direction of propagation.

This condition ensures that the causal structure of light-like events is preserved across inertial frames. Requiring light-like worldlines to remain light-like is a minimal causality constraint that is both empirically motivated and necessary for a consistent relativistic kinematics.

We apply this postulate to light signals traveling along the common x-axis. The Einstein-gauge coordinates of an event on a light ray at $(t, c t)$ are translated to an event in S_v by the transformation (3.21):

$$t_v^{(+)} = (a + b c) t \quad (3.28)$$

$$x_v^{(+)} = e(c - v) t \quad (3.29)$$

For this to be a light ray in the positive x_v -direction in S_v , we require $x_v^{(+)} / t_v^{(+)} = c_v$.

Therefore,

$$\frac{e(c - v)}{a + b c} = c_v \quad (3.30)$$

Similarly the Einstein-gauge coordinates of an event on a light ray at $(t, -c t)$ are translated to an event in S_v :

$$t_v^{(-)} = (a - b c) t \quad (3.31)$$

$$x_v^{(-)} = e(-c - v) t \quad (3.32)$$

For this to be a light ray in the negative x_v -direction in S_v , we require $x_v^{(-)} / t_v^{(-)} = -c_v$.

Therefore,

$$\frac{e(c + v)}{a - b c} = c_v \quad (3.33)$$

Equations (3.30) and (3.33) both equal c_v . Setting them equal to each other and after the appropriate algebra we obtain:

$$b = -a \frac{v}{c^2} \quad (3.34)$$

Finally substituting (3.34) and (3.26) in (3.21) we obtain

$$\mathbf{M} = e \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{v}{w} & \frac{1}{w} \frac{v^2}{c^2} & 0 & 0 \\ -v & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.35)$$

Furthermore substituting (3.34) and (3.26) in equation (3.33), yields

$$c_v = \frac{e(c + v)}{a - b c} = c \frac{w}{v} \quad (3.36)$$

imposing a constraint on the relative speeds and Einstein-gauge light-speeds between inertial frames.

3.7: Kinematic Symmetry in the Einstein Gauge

Postulate: The magnitude of the relative speed between two inertial frames, as measured within their respective Einstein-gauge coordinate systems, is reciprocal. If the origin of frame S_v moves with Einstein-gauge velocity $+v$ along the x -axis of frame S , then the origin of frame S moves with Einstein-gauge velocity $-v$ along the x_v -axis of frame S_v .

To determine the relationship between w and v , and between c_v and c , a further physical assumption is required. The most natural, but non-trivial, assumption is the reciprocity of Einstein-gauge velocities:

$$w = -v \quad (3.37)$$

The Einstein-gauge speeds v and w are derived from the physical speeds and the physical synchronization anisotropies $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ and $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_v$. If these anisotropies represent genuine properties of spacetime, then the equality $w = -v$ imposes a specific symmetry on

those properties across inertial frames. It asserts that the operational procedure for measuring relative Einstein-gauge speed yields equal and opposite values. This condition has both operational significance—it is testable using two-way radar measurements within each frame [16, 17, 21, 22]—and foundational importance, as it connects to the symmetry principles underlying special relativity [14, 20, 22]. It is operationally equivalent to demanding that the inverse transformation is obtained, up to a scale, by simply reversing the velocity parameter [21, 22], i.e., $\mathbf{M}^{-1}(v) \propto \mathbf{M}(-v)$ which is only one step from the Principle of Relativity formality [7, 8, 9].

Imposing $w = -v$ simplifies the matrix (3.35) to:

$$\mathbf{M} = e \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{v}{c^2} & 0 & 0 \\ -v & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.38)$$

Further substitution of $w = -v$ in equation (3.36) forces the conclusion:

$$c_v = c \quad (3.39)$$

Thus, the kinematic symmetry postulate also forces the Einstein-gauge light speed to be a universal constant c across all frames making it an emergent property rather than a separate postulate [7, 8, 9, 21].

Equation (3.38) and invertability condition do not determine the scaling parameters e and e_v individually. This leaves a one-parameter family of solutions, representing a previously overlooked residual conventional freedom in the choice of scale for the Einstein-gauge coordinates of different frames.

Two distinct interpretive paths emerge:

1. *The Privileged Frame Interpretation:* One may choose a specific inertial frame (say, S_0) and assign its scaling factor a convenient value, e.g., $E_0=1$. Equation (3.38) then dictates the scaling factor for any other frame S_v moving at speed v relative to S_0 (from (3.27) and(3.37)) :

$$e_v = 1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \quad (3.40)$$

In this scheme, the frame S_0 is metrologically privileged; its Einstein-gauge coordinates are "natural" or "unscaled." All other frames have their spatial and temporal units scaled by e_v . While logically and mathematically consistent, this introduces a preferred frame through convention.

2. *The Symmetric Scale Interpretation:* complete equivalence among inertial frames—not just in the laws of physics but also in the *scale* of their Einstein-gauge coordinates—can be achieved by scale symmetry condition, $e_v = e$, yielding:

$$e = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)^{-0.5} \quad (3.41)$$

This solution applies symmetrically to both frames. Furthermore, this choice has an appealing operational justification: it ensures that the coordinate distance to a distant star in the transverse plane is measured to be the same in both frames.

Adopting the symmetric scale interpretation yields the final, familiar form:

$$\mathbf{M} = \gamma \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{v}{c^2} & 0 & 0 \\ -v & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.42)$$

where $\gamma = (1 - v^2/c^2)^{-1}$ is the Lorentz boost.

This is the Lorentz transformation in the Einstein gauge. The path to it reveals that the standard formalism is the result of a specific set of choices which are all elegantly encapsulated in Einstein's first postulate and the empirical postulate of two-way speed isotropy.

4. Implications for Physical Synchronization Anisotropy

The derivation has produced the Lorentz transformation in the Einstein gauge, Eq. (3.42), under the postulates of kinematic symmetry ($w = -v$) and symmetric scaling ($e_v = e$). We now examine the consequences for the possible physical synchronization anisotropy κ .

The physical transformation $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$ corresponding to the Einstein-gauge Lorentz transformation is obtained via Eq. (2.4): $\bar{\mathbf{M}} = \mathbf{U}(\kappa_v) \mathbf{M} \mathbf{U}^{-1}(\kappa)$.

As shown in Sec. 3.7, for frames in standard configuration (relative motion along the x-axis), consistency with the alignment of the x-axis forces the anisotropy vectors to be purely longitudinal: $\kappa = (\kappa_x, 0, 0)$ and $\kappa_v = (\kappa_{vx}, 0, 0)$. The resulting physical transformation, given by Eq. (3.43), is mathematically consistent for any values κ_x and κ_{vx} with $|\kappa| < 1$;

$$\bar{\mathbf{M}} = \gamma \begin{bmatrix} 1 - \frac{v \kappa_{vx}}{c} & -\frac{\kappa_x}{c} - \frac{v}{c^2} + \frac{\kappa_x \kappa_{vx}}{c^2} + \frac{\kappa_{vx}}{c} & 0 & 0 \\ -v & v \frac{\kappa_x}{c} + 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

However, the postulates applied—kinematic symmetry and scale symmetry—are not specific to the x-axis. They govern the relationship between any two inertial frames. Consider a second pair of frames, S and S_u, in standard configuration with relative motion along the y-axis. Repeating the entire derivation for this configuration, the alignment of the y-axis would force the physical anisotropy vectors to be of the form $\kappa = (0, \kappa_y, 0)$ and $\kappa_u = (0, \kappa_{yu}, 0)$.

Our derivation assumes linear transformations between inertial frames, as justified by homogeneity and isotropy of space. In this framework, any nonzero constant κ would render the two-way light speed non-universal across frames. While nonlinear generalizations of κ could in principle maintain two-way isotropy locally [23], they would imply position-dependent synchronization rules inconsistent with the spatial homogeneity underlying special relativity.

The physical anisotropy κ is a property of the frame S . It must simultaneously satisfy the conditions arising from its relationship with a frame moving along x -axis as well as with a frame moving along y -axis. The only vector consistent with both constraints is:

$$\kappa = \mathbf{0} \tag{4.2}$$

By the same reasoning, $\kappa_{\mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{0}$. Therefore, the postulates of kinematic symmetry and scale symmetry force the physical synchronization anisotropy to vanish in all frames.

This has a profound interpretation: if kinematic symmetry (the reciprocity of Einstein-gauge velocities, $w = -v$) is empirically verified, then not only is the Einstein-gauge light speed c universal, but the one-way speed of light is physically isotropic in all inertial frames. The parameter κ , often discussed within the conventionality-of-simultaneity literature [2, 6, 12, 13, 24, 25], is shown to represent only a descriptive convention, not a physical degree of freedom, once kinematic symmetry is imposed.

Consequently, the Lorentz transformation in the Einstein gauge, Eq. (3.42), corresponds to the physical transformation between frames with isotropic one-way light propagation. The foundational postulates of special relativity—the principle of relativity and the constancy of the one-way speed of light—are thus derived from the more minimal set: two-way light speed isotropy, light-like interval preservation, kinematic symmetry, and scale symmetry. The latter two are testable operational conditions that, if

confirmed, elevate the one-way light speed constancy from a convention to a physical fact.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we have demonstrated that the Lorentz transformation can be recovered using a minimal axiomatic set that relies exclusively on operationally definable quantities. Starting only from the isotropy of the two-way speed of light—a result firmly established by experiments from Michelson–Morley to modern laser tests [3,4,18,19]—we introduced an *Einstein gauge* to handle synchronization conventions explicitly. Imposing a single additional condition, the reciprocity of radar-measured velocities between inertial frames $w = -v$, uniquely selects the Lorentz transformation and forces the one-way speed of light to be isotropic and universal.

A key outcome of this derivation is the physical status of the synchronization parameter κ . While often regarded as a matter of convention in the literature [2,6,12,13], we have shown that if kinematic reciprocity holds, κ must vanish in all inertial frames. This demonstrates that the oft-debated “conventionality of simultaneity” reduces to a mathematical redundancy rather than a physical degree of freedom, provided the empirical symmetry of velocity reciprocity is confirmed. The result thus bridges the test-theory framework of Mansouri–Sexl and Robertson [14,15] with the operational kinematics of special relativity.

Our work offers two logically distinct pathways to the full structure of special relativity:

1. **Empirically grounded path:** two-way light isotropy + kinematic reciprocity → Lorentz transformation + one-way constancy.
2. **Conventionally grounded path:** one-way constancy + internal consistency → Lorentz transformation + relativity principle.

In both cases, one of the traditional postulates of special relativity is derived rather than assumed, clarifying the theory's logical architecture and its connection to measurable quantities.

From an experimental perspective, the kinematic reciprocity condition $w = -v$ is directly testable using existing technologies—such as global navigation satellite systems, or precision radar experiments. A confirmation of this symmetry would not only validate the Lorentz transformation but also empirically establish the one-way isotropy of light as a necessary consequence within the theory. Conversely, any violation would open a window onto possible physical anisotropies in spacetime synchronization, with implications for foundational physics beyond standard relativity [26,27].

In summary, this derivation provides a minimal, operationally transparent axiomatic basis for special relativity, replacing Einstein's two postulates with more elementary and testable conditions. It also situates the discussion of synchronization conventions within a framework that distinguishes clearly between mathematical description and physical reality. While not altering the empirical predictions of relativity, this approach refines our understanding of its foundations and offers a clear pathway for future experimental scrutiny.

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